

N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid as Donor

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N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid is used as a reagent for spectrophotometric, gravimetric analysis of various metal ions¹⁻⁶. Since the studies with the rare earths metal ions are very limited it is desirable to discuss the structure of complexes of rare earths by means of infrared and ultraviolet spectra.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A. R. or G. R. or B. D. H. or E. Merck respectively unless otherwise specified. The N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the method of Priyadarshini and Tandon m. p. 121°, reported⁷ 121°. The procedure for preparing the metal complexes is essentially the same as described elsewhere⁸.

The infrared spectra of metal complexes were recorded on Perkin Elmer 221 spectrophotometer as KBr pellets and ultraviolet spectra were recorded on Carry 14 spectrophotometer by dissolving the metal complexes in ethanol.

Results and Discussion

The infrared vibration frequencies are given in Table 1. The ultraviolet spectral data with their assignments are given in Table 2.

These complexes are sparingly soluble in organic solvents except ethanol in which they are fairly soluble. The O-H stretching vibration of N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid, I, is assigned in the region⁹ of 3250 cm⁻¹. This band disappears in the metal complexes as the replacement hydrogen of the hydroxylamino group by the metal ions and formation of metal oxygen bond (II). Similarly the carbonyl vibration at 1650 cm⁻¹ in N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid is shifted to lower frequencies region at 1590 cm⁻¹. The lower shift is due to the formation of coordination bond like -O-M←O=C.

TABLE 1—INFRARED SPECTRA OF RARE EARTHS N-PHENYLBENZOHYDROXAMATE COMPLEXES

Compd. No.	Molecular Formula	m. p.	$\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{N-O}
I	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₄	Zr 250 ^d	1597	928
II	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₃	La 150	1592	935
III	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₃	Ce 120	1598	929
IV	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₃	Pr 133	1595	932
V	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₃	Nd 140	1599	927
VI	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₃	Sm 157	1596	937
VII	[C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NO ₂] ₄	Th 162	1598	928

d = decomposed

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TABLE 2—UV SPECTRA OF RARE EARTH COMPLEXES

Compd. No.	Metal Ions	λ_{max} (nm)	Wave number cm ⁻¹	Assignment
I	Zr	270	36270	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
II	La	275	36360	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
III	Ce	320	31250	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
IV	Pr	290	37930	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
V	Nd	285	35080	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
VI	Sm	285	35080	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}
VII	Th	285	35080	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}

The special behaviour of lanthanides is fundamentally different from that of d-block elements. The basic reasons for the differences lies in the fact that the electrons responsible for magnetic spectral properties of lanthanides ions of 4f electron and 4f orbitals are very effectively shielded from interaction with external forces by the overlapping 5s² and 5p⁶ shells. The bands may be assigned to the transitions in which an f electron is excited to an outer d, s or p orbital¹⁰ and the spectra have been assigned to 4f-5d transitions¹¹.

The spectra of the complexes of typical of octahedral La (III) complexes. The bands around 36400cm⁻¹ have been assigned to transitions derived from ⁴A_{2g} - ⁴T_{1g} in the octahedral field correspondance to Dq values. The spectrochemical series of metals as obtained for complexes are

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